

KNOWLEDGE AUTOMATION AND EMPLOYEE CREATIVITY (KAEC) MECHANISM FOR POLICY MAKERS IN THE BANKING SECTOR

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Abstract

The particular interest in this research includes developing Knowledge Automation and Employee Creativity (KAEC) mechanism for policy makers to strengthen organizational efficiency and effectiveness from managing knowledge perspective. The literature review emphasizes the connectivity of knowledge automation and employee creativity. The literature does not provide any mechanism to measure and find the connectivity of knowledge automation and employee creativity particularly in the banking sector. In this regard, the research question is grounded on theoretical and empirical aspects. The theoretical aspect finds out the impact of knowledge management practices on employee creativity and the empirical aspect explores the evidence related to knowledge management and employee creativity. The mixed research methodology is applied using the inductive approach. The scale of knowledge automation is developed by applying six-phase framework of thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2016). The measures to rate employee creativity is adopted (Sigala & Chalkiti, 2015). Qualitative and quantitative data is gathered, descriptive and inferential statistics is applied for data analysis. The study proposes policy makers to use knowledge automation measuring scale (KAMS) as the part of knowledge management framework to measure the level of automated knowledge. The study also proposes strategists and bankers to use Knowledge Automation and Employee Creativity (KAEC) mechanism for assessing level of automated knowledge and to measure employee creativity.

INTRODUCTION

Literature highlights the relationship between knowledge automation and employee creativity, so there is a demand for mechanism to evaluate knowledge automation and employee creativity in organizations. Mechanisms are beneficial for policy makers to deduce policies.

Literature Review

Literature review is collection of selected topics that must carry information to express point of views of the nature of topics. The literature review sparks understanding on the research topic; it allows researcher to work in an expert manner, to make informed decisions and to get benefited from available knowledge (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

This section reviews literature of selected and related topics that gives an overview of topics required to understand knowledge, knowledge management process, measuring knowledge, automated knowledge, process mapping,

creativity and measuring creativity. Moving from board to narrowing down, this literature focuses on measuring knowledge automation and measuring employee creativity. Different points of views are given from the approaches of many researchers. It discusses the essence of knowledge automation and creativity.

The literature review is structured on conceptual foundations. Starting from the concepts of data, information, knowledge, wisdom, automation, process, and creativity, moving towards knowledge management process, measuring knowledge, and focusing on creativity. The selected literature review is based on knowledge pyramid (Russell, 1989), revised knowledge pyramid (Jennex & Bartczak, 2013), SECI (socialization, externalization, combination, and internalization) framework (Nonaka, I., & Takeuchi, 1995), measuring knowledge, process in organizations and creativity tests.

Figure 1: Structure of Research Paper

Automated Knowledge:

The constant changes and advancements in information and communication technologies including the automation in processes have directed towards the generation and creation of huge data sets which requires contemporary methods for analyzing and managing data (Chang et al., 2019). Automated knowledge is the converted procedural knowledge of processes which carries steps of completing processes. Automated knowledge extracts knowledge from information and recommends specific knowledge to specific client. The level of automation affects the entire process of work, starting with the given information and building the task representation (Liang, T et al., 2016). The knowledge of people is represented through symbols and then embodied in systems, when system encodes, decodes, and

uses that knowledge it refers to automation (Gruber, 1989). In other words, when system represents people's knowledge it is called automated knowledge.

Knowledge Management

The term knowledge management is defined from many different perspectives in literature. (Giampaoli et al., 2017) defines knowledge management as an approach of attaining the related knowledge to the related people at the specific time and assisting people share information into actions for the purpose of enhancing organizational performance. According to (Semertzaki, 2017) knowledge management is having the ability to collect, process, and use data to enhance tasks and processes which are held on daily basis in

organizations and support long-term strategic planning processes.

The value of knowledge management is recognized in the 1990s. Knowledge is considered as the base of creating innovation and competitive advantage as it can focus on challenges and opportunities which organizations face in global economy. For building and maintaining core competencies in organizations, knowledge management is focused for creating, validating, formatting, distributing, and applying knowledge in organizations to learn, reflect and relearn (Tian, 2017). (Nonaka, I., 2009) highlights the secret of success of organizations as the unique approach to managing the creating of new knowledge.

Knowledge management identifies knowledge assets and then uses it for growing organization through a mechanism of capturing, identifying, creating, codifying, organizing and transferring intellectual assets that are crucial to the organization's performance related to knowledge intensive tasks (Rothberg & Erickson, 2017). To create competitive advantage, knowledge assets are coordinated through knowledge management which obtains and uses resources through which individuals get, access, and share the information to increase the level of individual knowledge (Uden & He, 2017).

Knowledge Management and Knowledge Automation:

The essence of knowledge management allows visualizing from the different angles and connects the dots of information for solving problem. Organizations that implement knowledge management improve the ability to create and incorporate information from many sources with

the help of tools and techniques of data analytics or data science (Chang et al., 2019). Automation means having a software or hardware which automatically performs tasks or processes without any form of human intervention (Evans, 1991). Industries where tasks and processes are repetitive, automation is used with the help of computers, control systems and operating equipment (Shekhar, 2019). When repetitive tasks are performed automatically, it allows individuals to focus more on other intellectual tasks which require judgment and thought. Employees get benefited from automation if the processes or tasks are complemented by automation (Autor, 2015).

Knowledge Management in Banking Sector

The continuous and repetitive tasks are the part of banking activities. That is why it is important to have synchronization between technology and social process in banks. With the help of information technology and automated knowledge management processes, banking sector can boost their performances (Narvind Kumar et al., 2023).

During the last year's banks emphasized actively on manual processes. This was resulted creation of information systems within banks. These information systems helped banks to organize their processes and resources. A failure of last information system is creation of massive amount of data and information, which resulted overload of information. This incident occurs when banks have quantity of surplus of information and they take time to search the related information and to choose the best to use. When there are the loads of information it could have like the consequence of the less reactive answers. As a result, the knowledge becomes more and more an imminent question of research in last periods.

The banking sector is one where high management practices are held and speed to cope with the competition is required by the international alliances in this business (Alhousary & Underwood, 2016). (Abbas et al., 2013) concludes in the study that banking industry of Pakistan requires developing positive relationship between knowledge sharing and knowledge activities which can promote the knowledge creation process. Banking sector needs to be able to understand knowledge management better to find ways to practice knowledge management strategies for effective performance and for creating knowledge responsive culture. The study that knowledge activities must be focused to increase the performance of banking sector.

Knowledge Automation and Employee Creativity

Many scholars have focused the bond and connection between knowledge and creativity. From the perspective of knowledge management (Chang et al., 2019) identifies three types skills in customer focused organizations, interpersonal

skills, organizational skills, and a blend of both. Creativity is a soft skill which is an important domain of performance specifically where knowledge is used and shared among employees. Knowledge sharing allows generating creative idea by establishing strong social capital which stimulates individuals to a divergent frame of thinking and brain storming (Rhee & Choi, 2017).

(Botega & Da Silva, 2020) states knowledge plays a very important role in the success of organization as managing knowledge on creativity is progressively significant to organizations create a competitive edge. Empirical evidence reveals that involvement of employees in SECI enhances individual creativity, individuals who engage in the process of knowledge creation and knowledge sharing are more creative (Baldé et al., 2018). Literature provide many evidences related to knowledge automation and creativity. The summary literature (Table 1) highlights the connection between automation and creativity. The essence of these evidence proves that the increase in knowledge automation increases

Table 1: Summary Literature on Knowledge Automation and Creativity

Year	Author/s	Focus	Approach/ Method	Findings/Contributions
2020	Luiz Fernando de Carvalho Botega, Jonny Carlos da Silva	Knowledge management and creativity	Prototype design	Designed a prototype of knowledge-based system for knowledge management on the choice of creativity and innovation techniques.
2019	Mark Muro, Robert Maxim, Jacob Whifton	The effect of machines on people and places	Backward and forward looking analyses	Impact of automation is studied from 1980 to 2016 and from 2016 to 2030 of 800 occupations.
2019	Zachary Kaiser	Creativity and automated teaching design	Exploratory method	The automated teaching design processes serve as creative problem-solving machines.

2018	Mariama Baldé, Aristides I. Ferreira, Travis Maynard	Knowledge creation and individual creativity	Deductive approach	SECI model of knowledge creation facilitates the relationship between intrinsic motivation, team level, individual level creativity, & trust.
2017	Eva Semertzaki	Knowledge managers and soft skills	Literature review	Competencies required by originations for knowledge professionals to accept new challenges and seize new opportunities in the increasingly volatile workplace.
2017	Daniele Giampaoli , Massimo Ciambotti Bontis	Knowledge management and creative problem solving	Deductive approach	Infrastructure impacts creativity. It enhances the ability to solve creative problem-solving solutions.

The Knowledge Automation and Employee Creativity (KAEC) Mechanism

The KAEC mechanism (Figure 2) assists to evaluate the level of knowledge automation, assesses employee creativity, helps to find the validity and reliability of knowledge

automation and employee creativity. The KAEC mechanism has five stages which will be beneficial for policy makers to deduce policy related to knowledge management framework.

Figure 2: The KAEC Mechanism

The First Stage: Identify Processes for Mapping

The first stage of KAEC mechanism is to identify processes for mapping. In the first stage, from major processes of organizations top processes are identified for mapping.

The Second Stage: Use Knowledge Automation Measuring Scale (KAMS) for Rating the Level of Knowledge Automation in Processes

The second stage of KAEC mechanism is the use of Knowledge Automation Measuring Scale (KAMS) for rating the level of knowledge automation in processes. The KAMS is developed by (Bhutto & Shaikh, 2020) for measuring the level of association of machine in a process. With the help of KAMS, processes are mapped.

Figure 3: Knowledge Automation Measuring Scale

(Bhutto & Shaikh, 2020)

The Third Stage: Assess Creativity in Employees

The third stage of KAEC mechanism is assessing creativity in employees. For assessing employee creativity 13-item measuring scale (Sigala & Chalkiti, 2015) are adopted and rated on Likert's 5-point scale (Likert, R., 1932).

The Fourth Stage: Determine The Validity of Knowledge Automation Level and Reliability of Employee Creativity:

The fourth stage of KAEC mechanism is determining the validity of knowledge automation level and finding the reliability of employee creativity. In this stage content

validity through experts is found and reliability statistics is measured by using statistical analysis tool (SPSS 20.0).

The Fifth Stage: Evaluate the Relationship between Knowledge Automation and Employee Creativity:

The fifth stage of KAEC mechanism is to evaluate the relationship between knowledge automation and employee creativity. To find out the relationship between variables, ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) test is conducted by using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). The relationship between variable are hypothesized and validated.

As per the demand of State Bank of Pakistan's strategic plan, vision 2020 (Strategic Planning Department, SBP, 2015), the key activity is to develop a knowledge management framework. The strategic goal 'SG6' highlights strengthening organizational efficiency and effectiveness. To achieve strategic goal, SBP has demand the implementation of modern knowledge management framework. The developed KAMS contributes as a part of knowledge management framework for the evaluation of knowledge automation in the processes.

Conclusion

The literature review concludes by reviewing the literature on topics related to the study. The concepts on data, information, knowledge, wisdom, automation, process, and creativity, connects with knowledge management process, measuring knowledge, and employee creativity. The selected and necessary literature review is based on knowledge pyramid, revised knowledge pyramid, SECI (socialization, externalization, combination, and internalization) framework, Bohn's eight-scale stages, and creativity tests. Starting from broader areas of knowledge management and creativity, the literature review narrows down to knowledge automation and employee creativity.

Contributions to Science, Technology and Innovation Policy

As per the demand of State Bank of Pakistan's strategic plan, vision 2020 (Strategic Planning Department, SBP, 2015), the key activity is to develop a knowledge management framework. The strategic goal 'SG6' highlights strengthening organizational efficiency and effectiveness. To

achieve strategic goal, SBP has demand the implementation of modern knowledge management framework. The developed KAMS contributes as a part of knowledge management framework for the evaluation of knowledge automation in the processes

Recommendations

This section provides the recommendations for policy makers, strategists, and researchers.

Recommendations for Policy makers

The study proposes policy makers to use KAMS as the part of knowledge management framework to measure the level of automated knowledge. The study proposes strategists and bankers to use Knowledge Automation and Employee Creativity (KAEC) mechanism for assessing level of automated knowledge and to evaluate employee creativity.

Reference:

- Abbas, F., Rasheed, A., Habiba, U., & Shahzad, I. (2013). Factors promoting knowledge sharing & knowledge creation in banking sector of Pakistan. *Management Science Letters*, 3(2), 405-414. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2012.12.031>
- Alhousary, T., & Underwood, J. (2016). Knowledge Sharing Culture: A Study On The Omani Commercial Banking Sector. *Eurasian Journal of Business and Management*, 4(3), 1-12.
- Autor, D. H. (2015). Why Are There Still So Many Jobs? The History and Future of Workplace Automation. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 29(3), 3-30. <https://doi.org/10.1257/jep.29.3.3>
- Baldé, M., Ferreira, A. I., & Maynard, T. (2018). SECI driven creativity: The role of team trust and intrinsic motivation. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 22(8), 1688-1711. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-06-2017-0241>
- Bhutto, A., & Shaikh, S. (2020). Intrapreneurial Culture through Think Tanks in Higher Education Institutions. *Journal of Information Technology*

- Management, Online First.
<https://doi.org/10.22059/jitm.2020.76294>
- Botega, L. F. D. C., & Da Silva, J. C. (2020). An artificial intelligence approach to support knowledge Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2016). Misconceptualising themes, thematic analysis, and other problems with Fugard and Potts' (2015) sample-size tool for thematic analysis. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 19(6), 739–743. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13645579.2016.1195588>
- Chang, H.-C., Wang, C.-Y., & Hawamdeh, S. (2019). Emerging trends in data analytics and knowledge management job market: Extending KSA framework. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 23(4), 664–686. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-02-2018-0088>
- Evans, G. (1991). Solving home automation problems using artificial intelligence techniques. *IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics*, 37(3), 395–400. <https://doi.org/10.1109/30.85542>
- Giampaoli, D., Ciambotti, M., & Bontis, N. (2017). Knowledge management, problem solving and performance in top Italian firms. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 21(2), 355–375. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-03-2016-0113>
- Gruber, T. R. (1989). Automated Knowledge Acquisition for Strategic Knowledge. In S. Marcus (Ed.), *Knowledge Acquisition: Selected Research and Commentary* (pp. 47–90). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4613-1531-5_6
- Jennex, M. E., & Bartczak, S. E. (2013). A Revised Knowledge Pyramid: *International Journal of Knowledge Management*, 9(3), 19–30. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijkm.2013070102>
- Liang, T, Mehta, S., & Mahmud, G. (2016). U.S. Patent Application No. 14/863,180.
- Likert, R. (1932). A technique for the measurement of attitudes. *Archives of Psychology*.
- management on the selection of creativity and innovation techniques. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 24(5), 1107–1130. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-10-2019-0559>
- Narvind Kumar, Khoso, I., & Shah, A. B. (2023). The Impact of Corporate Social Responsibility on Financial Performance: Evidence from the Listed Banks in Pakistan. *Journal of Peace, Development & Communication*, 07(01), 88–100. <https://doi.org/10.36968/JPDC-V07-101-09>
- Nonaka, I. (2009). The knowledge-creating company. In *The Economic Impact of Knowledge*, 175–187.
- Nonaka, I., & Takeuchi. (1995). *The knowledge-creating company: How Japanese companies create the dynamics of innovation*. Oxford university press.
- Rhee, Y. W., & Choi, J. N. (2017). Knowledge management behavior and individual creativity: Goal orientations as antecedents and in-group social status as moderating contingency. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 38(6), 813–832. <https://doi.org/10.1002/job.2168>
- Rothberg, H. N., & Erickson, G. S. (2017). Big data systems: Knowledge transfer or intelligence insights? *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 21(1), 92–112. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-07-2015-0300>
- Russell, A. (1989). From data to wisdom. *Journal of Applied Systems Analysis*, 16(1), 3–9.
- Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research methods for business: A skill building approach*. John Wiley & sons.
- Semertzaki, E. (2017). Knowledge Management Skills Applicable to Information Management – Information Management Skills Applicable to Knowledge Management in an Organization☆. In J. M. Matarazzo & T. Pearlstein (Eds.), *The Emerald Handbook of Modern Information Management* (pp. 571–604). Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-78714-525-220171023>

Shekhar, S. S. (2019). Artificial Intelligence in Automation. *Research Review International Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 4(6), 14-17.

Sigala, M., & Chalkiti, K. (2015). Knowledge management, social media and employee creativity. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 45, 44-58.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2014.11.003>

Tian, X. (2017). Big data and knowledge management: A case of déjà vu or back to the future? *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 21(1), 113-131. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-07-2015-0277>

Uden, L., & He, W. (2017). How the Internet of Things can help knowledge management: A case study from the automotive domain. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, 21(1), 57-70. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JKM-07-2015-0291>